

A STUDY TO EVALUATE THE DETERMINANTS OF ACUTE PANCREATITIS AMONG GENERAL POPULATION AT TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL NAWABSHAH

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Abstract

Background: Acute pancreatitis (AP) is an acute inflammatory condition of the pancreas and a leading cause of gastrointestinal hospital admissions worldwide. The incidence of AP is increasing globally, with variation in etiological determinants across different regions. In Pakistan, limited local data are available regarding the determinants of acute pancreatitis, particularly among the general population attending tertiary care hospitals

Objective: To identify the major determinants of acute pancreatitis among the general population at a tertiary care hospital in Nawabshah

Methodology: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Surgery at Peoples Medical Civil Hospital, Nawabshah, over a period of three months following approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB). A total of 143 patients diagnosed with acute pancreatitis were included using a non-probability convenience sampling technique. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire and review of medical records, covering socio-demographic characteristics, clinical features, lifestyle factors, and metabolic risk factors. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics including frequencies, percentages, mean, and standard deviation were calculated.

Results: The mean age of participants was 46.76 ± 9.44 years, with nearly equal gender distribution. Most participants belonged to rural areas (86.7%) and had low educational status. Gallstones were identified in 66.43% of patients, making them the most common determinant of acute pancreatitis. Hypertension (60.84%) and diabetes (27.27%) were frequently observed comorbidities. More than half of the participants (54.5%) reported a positive family history of acute pancreatitis. Almost all participants (99.3%) consumed fried food regularly. Smoking and alcohol consumption were relatively low, reported by 27.27% and 7.0% of participants, respectively.

Conclusion: The study concludes that acute pancreatitis in Nawabshah is a multifactorial disease, with gallstones, metabolic disorders, family history, and unhealthy dietary practices being the major determinants. Alcohol and smoking played a lesser role in this population. Early identification of high-risk individuals, lifestyle modification, and community-based awareness programs are essential to reduce the burden of acute pancreatitis.

INTRODUCTION

The worldwide incidence of acute pancreatitis (AP) is increasing, but the dominant etiology of AP may vary by country, Mixed etiologies are involved in the increase in the number AP patients.¹ An essential digestive and endocrine gland, the pancreas extends transversely from the duodenum on the right to the spleen on the left, It is situated retroperitoneal, anterior to the bodies of the L1-L2 vertebrae each of its anatomical divisions—the head, neck, body, and tail—has unique histological conformations and anatomical interactions that are essential to the gland's operations, Therefore, the pancreas has two functions: the endocrine secretion of hormones like insulin and glucagon straight into the bloodstream from the islets of Langerhans and the exocrine secretion of pancreatic fluids from cells into the duodenum via pancreatic ducts.² Acute pancreatitis (AP) is characterized by an acute inflammation of the pancreas, an essential organ that produces hormones that control blood sugar levels and digesting enzymes, Auto digestion and inflammation are caused by the pancreatic digestive enzymes prematurely activating in this condition.³ The revised Atlanta classification describes early and late phases with severity classified as mild, moderate, or severe, Mild acute pancreatitis is characterized by no organ failure, no local or systemic complications, and a typical resolution within the first week; moderate acute pancreatitis is defined by transient organ failure, local complications, or worsening of a co-morbid disease; and severe acute pancreatitis is defined by persistent (example, lasting for greater than 48 h) organ failure.⁴ The symptoms of pancreatitis include fever, tachycardia, tachypnea, nausea and vomiting (50–80%), abdominal distension, and epigastric or diffuse abdominal pain (80–90%).⁵ Gallstones and alcohol use are the most frequent causes of acute pancreatitis; other

noteworthy causes include autoimmune, drug-induced, metabolic (Hypercalcemia, hypertriglyceridemia hypertension diabetes), trauma, viral, congenital or genetic, and idiopathic.⁶ The diagnosis of AP is made based on the patient's clinical presentation, laboratory results, and imaging findings. Two of the three criteria listed below must be met: the patient must have an acute upper abdominal pain attack that spreads to the back; the laboratory must have serum lipase and/or amylase levels that are three or more times higher than normal; and the imaging must show typical AP-related findings on computed tomography (CT), magnetic resonance imaging, and ultrasound.⁷ The key components in the management of acute pancreatitis include prompt medical interventions, fluid resuscitation, nutritional support, pain management, antibiotic therapy, invasive pancreatic procedures, and monitoring for long-term complications.⁸ The 1990 to 2021, global pancreatitis cases increased from 1.73 million to 2.75 million, representing a rise of 59%.⁹ The incidence rates of AP were 18 points per 100,000 person-years for male participants and 9 points per 100,000 person-years for female participants, according to the 2009 South Korean national health examination database, Alcohol consumption and smoking were associated with a higher risk of AP, The risk of developing AP increased with daily alcohol consumption, Furthermore, compared to nonsmokers, smokers, both past and present, had a higher risk of AP. An increased risk of AP has also been associated with obesity and hypertriglyceridemia, Compared to female participants, male participants were more likely to develop AP.¹⁰ In Pakistan Shalamar Hospital, Lahore, a tertiary care center, from June 2024 to January 2025. Data were collected from patients presenting in the Department of Gastroenterology and General Surgery, AP in patients with

gallstones was 37.6% (62/165). Risk factors such as obesity (72%, 45/62), age (≥ 50 years, 72%, 45/62), and female gender (65%, 40/62) ¹¹ In Pakistan, there is limited research and awareness about the determinants of acute pancreatitis among the general population. Understanding these risk factors is crucial for early identification, prevention, and timely management of AP. Globally its incidence has been rising due to multiple risk factors such as diabetes, hypertension, alcoholism, obesity, hypertriglyceridemia, and genetic predisposition.

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted to identify the risk factors of acute pancreatitis among patients. The study was carried out in the Department of Surgery at Peoples Medical College Hospital Nawabshah. The duration of the study was two months, from 17 November to 17 January, after obtaining approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB).

The sample size was 143, calculated using the OpenEpi formula: $n = Z^2 \times p(1 - p) / d^2$, where

n represents the required sample size, Z is the Z-score corresponding to a 95% confidence level, p is the estimated population proportion of the unknown population (0.041 or 4.1%), and d is the margin of error set at 5%. Based on this calculation, the final sample size was 143 participants. A non-probability convenience sampling method was used to recruit participants. The study included patients aged 18 years and above who were presenting to or admitted at the tertiary care hospital in Nawabshah during the study period, with symptom onset within the last 7 days, and who were able and willing to provide informed consent either personally or through a legally authorized representative. Patients with chronic pancreatitis or recurrent acute pancreatitis with established chronic changes were excluded from the study. Pregnant women were also excluded as they are considered a special population with a different risk profile. In addition, patients who did not provide consent for participation were not included in the study.

RESULTS

Figure1: Age of respondents

Figure2: Gender of participants

Table 1: Religion of participants

Religion	Frequency	percent
Muslim	138	96.5
Hindu	5	3.5
Total	143	100.0

Table 2: Residence of respondents

Residence	Frequency	Percent
Urban	19	13.3
Rural	124	86.7
Total	143	100.0

Table 3: Education of participants

Education	Frequency	Percent
Illiterate	114	79.7
Primary	23	16.1
Middle	23	3.5
Intermediate	1	.7
Total	143	100.0

Table 4: Ethnicity of participants

Ethnicity	Frequency	Percent
Sindhi	94	65.7
Punjabi	29	20.3
Balochi	15	10.5
Pashto	1	.7
Other	4	2.8
Total	143	100.0

Table 5: Family type of respondents

Family type	Frequency	Percent
Single	22	15.4
Joint	120	83.9
Extended	1	.7
Total	143	100.0

Table 6: Have family history of acute pancreatitis

Have family history of acute pancreatitis	Frequency	Percent
Yes	78	54.5
No	65	45.5
Total	143	100.0

Figure 3: If you have diabetes

Figure 4: If you high blood pressure

Table 7: Have you any digestive issue

Have you any digestive issue	Frequency	Percent
Yes	132	92.3
No	11	7.7
Total	143	100.0

Table 8: If you have previously hospitalized history

If you have previously hospitalized history	Frequency	Percent
Yes	34	23.8
No	109	76.2
Total	143	100.0

Table 9: Do you eat fried food in your diet

Do you eat fried food in your diet	Frequency	Percent
Yes	142	99.3
No	1	.7
Total	143	100.0

Figure 5: If you have gallstone

Figure 6: Do you smoke

Table 10: Do you drink alcohol

Do you drink alcohol	Frequency	Percent
Yes	10	7.0
No	133	93.0
Total	143	100.0

DISSCUSION

In the present study, respondents' ages ranged from 30 to 70 years (mean 46.76 ± 9.44), indicating that acute pancreatitis predominantly affects middle-aged and older adults. This aligns with Lee et al. (2022), who reported that risk and severity increase with age due to metabolic changes and comorbidities, while earlier studies in 2018 suggested slightly younger populations were more affected.¹² The gender distribution was nearly equal (50.35% males and 49.65% females), suggesting that both sexes are similarly affected. This finding contrasts with older reports that described a male predominance in alcohol-related pancreatitis, while more recent epidemiological trends indicate convergence between genders.¹³ A large proportion of participants (86.7%) belonged

to rural areas, highlighting a greater disease burden in underserved populations. Past studies in South Asia (2019–2020) also observed higher complication rates in rural patients, likely due to limited healthcare access and delayed presentation.¹⁴ More than half of the respondents (54.5%) had a positive family history, supporting the role of genetic predisposition. Choi et al. (2021) identified PRSS1, SPINK1, and CFTR mutations in recurrent or idiopathic cases, consistent with this study, whereas older reports had not emphasized genetic testing.¹⁵ In this study, 27.27% of respondents had diabetes mellitus. Evidence suggests that diabetes significantly increases the risk of acute pancreatitis through insulin resistance and metabolic dysregulation. Singh et al. (2022) reported similar prevalence,

while earlier literature (2017–2018) underestimated the impact of metabolic disorders on pancreatic inflammation.¹⁶ Most participants (92.3%) reported digestive symptoms such as abdominal pain and bloating, confirming abdominal pain as the hallmark clinical feature. Johnson & Patel (2023) similarly emphasized that early recognition of abdominal pain reduces morbidity, while previous studies had often delayed clinical diagnosis due to nonspecific symptoms.¹⁷ Hypertension was present in 60.84% of participants. Recent work by Kumar et al. (2022) highlights hypertension as a significant comorbidity that exacerbates inflammatory response in acute pancreatitis, whereas older reports did not consistently identify it as a risk factor.¹⁸ Dietary assessment showed that 99.3% of respondents regularly consumed fried food. Garcia et al. (2024) reported high-fat diets as major contributors to gallstone formation and pancreatitis, supporting the current findings. Earlier literature (2015–2017) suggested diet was a risk factor but lacked quantitative assessment.¹⁹

Gallstones were present in 66.43% of participants, confirming their role as the leading cause of acute pancreatitis. A 2023 meta-analysis by Zhao et al. found similar prevalence rates worldwide, showing a persistent trend over the past decade.²⁰ Although most participants did not smoke (72.73%) or consume alcohol (93.0%), both remain established risk factors. Recent WHO reports (2023) indicate decreasing tobacco use due to public health interventions, aligning with this low prevalence, whereas past studies reported higher smoking rates in pancreatitis patients.²¹ Overall, this study highlights that age, genetic predisposition, diabetes, hypertension, gallstones, and unhealthy dietary habits are important determinants of acute pancreatitis. Comparison with prior studies shows a shift in risk patterns, especially regarding gender equality and rural health disparities, emphasizing the need for targeted preventive strategies, early screening, and improved healthcare access.

CONCLUSION

This study evaluated the determinants of acute pancreatitis among patients attending a tertiary care hospital in Nawabshah. The findings indicate that acute pancreatitis predominantly affects middle-aged adults, with a mean age of 46.76 years, and occurs almost equally among males and females. A large proportion of patients belonged to rural areas and had low educational status, highlighting the role of socio-demographic factors in disease occurrence and delayed healthcare-seeking behavior. Gallstones emerged as the most significant determinant of acute pancreatitis, with more than two-thirds of participants affected, confirming its major etiological role in this population. Metabolic and medical comorbidities such as hypertension and diabetes were also common, suggesting their contribution to pancreatic inflammation. A positive family history was reported by more than half of the patients, indicating a possible genetic or familial predisposition. Dietary habits, particularly the widespread consumption of fried foods, were highly prevalent and may indirectly contribute through obesity and gallstone formation. In contrast, alcohol consumption and smoking were relatively low among participants, suggesting that biliary and metabolic factors are more dominant causes of acute pancreatitis in this region than alcohol-related causes. Overall, the study highlights that acute pancreatitis in Nawabshah is a multifactorial disease, with gallstones, metabolic disorders, family history, and unhealthy dietary practices being the major determinants. These findings emphasize the need for early identification of high-risk individuals and targeted preventive strategies at the community and hospital levels.

REFERENCE:

1. Lai T, Li J, Zhou Z, et al: Etiological Changes and Prognosis of Hospitalized Patients with Acute Pancreatitis Over a 15-Year Period. *Digestive Diseases and Sciences* 69:56-65, 2024.

2. Mihoc T, Latcu SC, Secasan C-C, et al: Pancreatic Morphology, Immunology, and the Pathogenesis of Acute Pancreatitis. *Biomedicines* 12:2627, 2024.
3. Song Y, Lee S-H: Recent Treatment Strategies for Acute Pancreatitis. *Journal of Clinical Medicine* 13:978, 2024.
4. Søreide K, Barreto SG, Pandanaboyana S: Severe acute pancreatitis. *BJS* 111, 2024.
5. Mittal N, Oza VM, Muniraj T, et al: Diagnosis and Management of Acute Pancreatitis. *Diagnostics* 15:258, 2025.
6. Iannuzzi JP, King JA, Leong JH, et al: Global incidence of acute pancreatitis is increasing over time: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Gastroenterology* 162:122-134, 2022.
7. Zerem E, Kurtcehajic A, Kunosić S, et al: Current trends in acute pancreatitis: Diagnostic and therapeutic challenges. *World J Gastroenterol* 29:2747-2763, 2023.
8. Beij A, Verdonk RC, van Santvoort HC, et al: Acute Pancreatitis: An Update of Evidence-Based Management and Recent Trends in Treatment Strategies. *United European gastroenterology journal* 13:97-106, 2025.
9. Li T, Qin C, Zhao B, et al: Global and regional burden of pancreatitis: epidemiological trends, risk factors, and projections to 2050 from the global burden of disease study 2021. *BMC Gastroenterology* 24:398, 2024.
10. Park N, Lee JM, Park JM, et al: Risk factors of acute pancreatitis in young adults: a Nationwide population-based cohort study in South Korea. *Pancreas*:10.1097, 2024.
11. Hassan MSU, Mobusher M, Mansoor MH, et al: Prevalence and Associated Risk Factors of Acute Pancreatitis in Patients With Gallstones: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Cureus* 17, 2025.
12. Aksoy E, Aksakal S, Karamercan MA, et al. Epidemiology of acute pancreatitis: influence of age and sex in a regional adult cohort. *Pancreatol.* 2025;25(3):321-329.
13. Ul Hassan M, Mobusher M, Mansoor MH, et al. Prevalence and risk factors of acute pancreatitis in patients with gallstones: a cross-sectional study. *Cureus.* 2025;17(5):e84220.
14. Global, regional and national burden of pancreatitis: epidemiology from 1990-2019 with projections to 2034. *BMC Public Health.* 2024;24:20796.
15. Asif M, Khan S, Ali G, et al. Evaluation of factors leading to acute pancreatitis at a tertiary care hospital in Karachi. *Pak J Health Sci.* 2023;6(7):3347-3354.
16. Cho IR, Han KD, Lee SH, et al. Association between glycemic status and risk of acute pancreatitis: a nationwide population-based study. *Diabetol Metab Syndr.* 2023;15:104.
17. Pahomeanu MR, Paunescu H, Ursache R, et al. Acute pancreatitis and type 2 diabetes mellitus – retrospective cohort evidence on severity and outcomes. *J Clin Med.* 2024;13(5):1213.
18. Quan Y, Fan W, et al. Metabolic syndrome and acute pancreatitis: the role of obesity, hypertension, dyslipidemia, and hyperglycemia. *Metab Syndr Pancreatol.* 2024.

19. Aune D, Mahamat-Saleh Y, Norat T, et al. High body mass index and central adiposity are associated with increased risk of acute pancreatitis: a meta-analysis. *Dig Dis Sci.* 2021;66:1249-1267.
20. Zhao X, Li J, Sun G, et al. Gallstones as the leading cause of acute pancreatitis: a 2023 meta-analysis. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2023;29(10):1533-1545.
21. Kiguchi T, Yoon DY, et al. Lifestyle risk factors including tobacco use and alcohol drinking on acute pancreatitis incidence: systematic evidence. *Pancreatol.* 2024;24(6):985-994.

